

Flood Vulnerability Mapping of Port Harcourt Nigeria, Using Geographical Information System and Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (GIS-MCDA)

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Abstract

Flooding is a major issue in Port Harcourt exacerbated by climate change. The city experiences annual flooding on a significant scale, with threats to the population and infrastructure. Poor urban planning, management, rapid urbanization, inadequate storm drainage systems, climate variability and extreme weather events, associated with climate change, are all contributing factors exacerbating the flooding issue in Port Harcourt. This study focuses on flood vulnerability mapping in Port Harcourt, integrating Geographical Information System and Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (GIS-MCDA) using selected variables including Elevation, Slope, Aspect, flow accumulation, flow direction, land surface temperature (LST), Rainfall, soil and Distance to stream to develop a vulnerability map. Findings revealed that the most predominant vulnerability level was High Vulnerability, which accounted for 49.87% of the total area, followed by Moderate Vulnerability at 40.53%, Low Vulnerability at 9.41%, Very Low Vulnerability at 0.17%, and Very High Vulnerability at 0.02%. For the statistical significance of the variables used, Rainfall, Slope, Distance from Streams and water body all contributed significantly to reducing deviance, as indicated by their small p-values, while Flow accumulation, Flow direction and Soil were not statistically significant due to their P-values greater than 0.05. The vulnerability maps obtained provides valuable information for flood mitigation and preparedness efforts. Hence, we recommend that high and moderate vulnerability areas calls for prioritizing measures like infrastructure improvements, early warning systems, and community awareness campaigns. Also, with a combination of vulnerability maps with information on population density, infrastructure, and land use, mitigation strategies could be tailored to specific contexts, especially in densely populated flood-prone locations with critical infrastructure.

Keywords: *Vulnerability, Rainfall, Slope, mitigation strategies, early warning systems.*

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Introduction

Studies have revealed that the Niger Delta region of Nigeria is only three meter above mean sea level and their coastline is dynamic in nature which renders hundreds of coastal communities exposed and vulnerable to climate change risk and hazards. The region is faced with seasonal flooding, increase in temperature, high precipitation, erosion, river salinization, ocean surges and siltation (Benson, 2020).

Flooding is major issue in Port Harcourt, exacerbated by climate change. The city experiences annual flooding on a significant scale, which poses threats to the population and infrastructure. Poor urban planning and management, rapid urbanization and inadequate storm drainage systems have been identified as contributing factors that contribute to and exacerbate the flooding issue in Port Harcourt. Improved planning practices and compliance with regulations are crucial for controlling the endemic flooding problem in the city (Echendu, 2021).

Climate variability and extreme weather events, such as heavy rainfall, associated with climate change, also contribute to increase flooding in the region (Weli & Efe, 2015). The changing climate patterns in Port Harcourt have implications for the health and wellbeing of the population (Stanley et al., 2021). Poor waste management practices, including improper disposal of waste and the generation of a significant amount of waste, further compound the flooding problem (Chukwu-Okeah & Deekor, 2020).

Understanding flood vulnerability and associated risks to climate change Impact amongst communities in Port Harcourt and Identifying highly vulnerable flood prone areas via vulnerability mapping is sacrosanct to addressing the challenges associated with the impact, which is needed for developing comprehensive strategies for climate change adaptation and resilience that incorporate the unique social, economic, and environmental characteristics of Port Harcourt, aimed at reducing susceptibility, vulnerability and increase

resilience to flooding and other impacts of climate change.

This study focuses on flood vulnerability zones in Port Harcourt, with the integration of Geographical information system and Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (GIS-MCDA) using selected variables which include; elevation, slope, aspect, flow accumulation, flow direction, land surface temperature (LST), amount of rainfall (AOR), soil, distance to stream. The flood vulnerability analysis features visualised geospatial maps for each of the selected factors (variables) as well as a vulnerability map which is an overlay that incorporates all the selected factors utilised, visualising flood vulnerability zones or very high to low vulnerability, with very high and high vulnerability zones indicating flood prone areas.

Literature Review

Glago (2021) explored the application of remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in flood hazard and vulnerability assessment. Remote sensing data provides valuable insights into factors like topography, land cover, and historical flood events, while GIS facilitates spatial analysis and modelling. Efficient evaluation of flood hazard has been achieved through the utilization of remote sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) methodologies. In the analysis of hazard and vulnerability, various techniques such as GIS overlay analysis, multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), fuzzy methods, and others have been employed. The combination of MCDA with GIS constitutes a versatile set of approaches for assessing and integrating geographic data and user expectations, thereby enhancing the decision-making process. The adaptability of the MCDA method makes it a prevalent choice for spatially reflecting flood vulnerability assessments, accommodating diverse and overlapping features.

Ugwu et al., (2022) investigated the flood vulnerability of developed properties (DPs) within Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria. Employing a data-driven approach, the study leveraged Open Street Map data for identifying

DPs, land use/land cover maps derived from 2020 Landsat imagery, soil texture data, elevation data and proximity to active river channels. The descriptive statistical analysis uncovered the presence of 44,014 Development Points (DPs) across the Port Harcourt Metropolis, revealing key findings regarding their flood vulnerability. Spatially, low vulnerability covered 60.78 sq. km (13.22%), moderate vulnerability extended over 259.72 sq. km (56.51%), and high vulnerability encompassed 139.14 sq. km (30.27%). In terms of property distribution, 3,977 DPs (9.04%) were in low vulnerability zones, 34,754 DPs (78.96%) in moderate vulnerability areas, and 5,283 DPs (12%) in high vulnerability zones. Notably, there was a significant concentration of DPs within moderately vulnerable zones. Their recommendations advocated for the prioritization of relocation for DPs in high vulnerability zones or the implementation of robust flood protection measures. Additionally, public awareness initiatives to discourage construction in highly and moderately vulnerable areas, integration of vulnerability maps into urban planning and development strategies for informed and data-driven decision-making to promote sustainable land use and reduce future flood risks.

Developing nations face a critical imperative, adapting to the realities of climate change. While the impacts are felt globally, mitigation efforts often require localized action. Tari et al., (2015) examined the specific risks posed by climate change to Port Harcourt's urban poor, a particularly vulnerable segment of the population. The study's key findings reveal that climate change poses multifaceted vulnerabilities across diverse sectors, encompassing environmental threats, health risks, food security challenges, and issues related to air and water pollution, flooding, and ecosystem disruption. Notably, the urban poor emerge as particularly susceptible to these impacts. Specific areas within Port Harcourt, including Diobu, D/Line, Port Harcourt Township, New GRAs, and parts of Obio/Akpor, were identified as vulnerable hotspots, experiencing recurrent flooding attributed to increased rainfall and rising temperatures, leading to ecological imbalances in

coastal regions. In response to these findings, the study recommended targeted policies and plans to mitigate and alleviate the impacts on the urban poor. These include investments in infrastructure development such as flood control measures, improved drainage systems, and resilient housing. Additionally, the study advocates for livelihood diversification by supporting alternative income sources and promoting climate-smart agriculture. The establishment of effective early warning systems and communication channels for disaster preparedness and the expansion of access to healthcare and sanitation facilities are also highlighted as crucial public health interventions. Collectively, these policy recommendations aim to address the specific vulnerabilities identified and foster resilience among the urban poor in Port Harcourt.

Flooding is acknowledged as a global challenge exacerbated by climate change, and in Nigeria, where the population of over 200 million faces numerous threats from recurrent flooding, it stands out as a pervasive environmental disaster. Port Harcourt, situated in Southern Nigeria, grapples with substantial annual flooding. Existing research has linked this phenomenon to deficient urban planning, yet minimal effort has been invested in engaging planning professionals to thoroughly investigate this association. Flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis is a significant issue that has been studied by various researchers. The lack of proper urban planning and management has been identified as a key factor contributing to the flooding problem in Port Harcourt (Echendu, 2021; Echendu & Georgeou, 2021). The relationship between urban planning, flooding, and sustainable development in Port Harcourt has been explored in depth (Echendu & Georgeou, 2021). It has been found that the city's rapid urbanization and inadequate storm drainage systems exacerbate the flooding issue (Dan-Jumbo et al., 2018). Additionally, the vulnerability of developed properties to flooding in Port Harcourt has been assessed using remote sensing and GIS techniques (Ugwu et al., 2022). The study found that flooding can result from various factors such as prolonged seasonal

rainfall, rainstorm, and inadequate storm drainage (Akukwe & Ogbodo, 2015).

The impact of lifestyle scenarios on household waste generation in Port Harcourt has also been investigated (Umunnakwe et al., 2019). The study revealed that a significant amount of waste is generated in the city, with organic waste being the largest component. Poor waste management practices, including indiscriminate dumping of waste in drainages and open spaces, contribute to the flooding problem (Chukwu-Okeah & Deekor, 2020). Furthermore, the study highlighted the need for effective waste management practices to address the waste-related challenges in Port Harcourt.

The health implications of flooding in Port Harcourt have been examined as well (Amaechi & Ordinioha, 2019). The study found an association between the 2017 flood and the morbidities experienced in the city. This highlights the need for measures to mitigate the health risks associated with flooding. The determinants of flooding in Port Harcourt have been analysed, and recommendations have been made to address the perennial flooding in the metropolis (Thecla, 2014). The study emphasizes the importance of understanding and addressing the underlying causes of flooding to effectively mitigate the issue. The impact of wetland reclamation and conversion on flooding in Port Harcourt has also been studied (Ibama & Nengi, 2020). The study highlights the challenges associated with urbanization and wetland conversion in the city and proposes planning measures to mitigate these problems.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The geographical location and topography of Port Harcourt play a significant role in various aspects, including environmental sustainability, flooding, and air pollution. The region's low-lying topography and lack of significant relief have implications for flooding, as rivers are characterized by sluggish flow velocity, leading to ponding in many parts and tidal conditions in others (Thecla, 2014). Additionally, the absence of high lands in the area allows airborne pollutants to travel fast and farthest,

contributing to air pollution concerns (Rufai et al., 2019; Obiweluzo et al., 2021). Furthermore, the Niger Delta region, where Port Harcourt is located, is vulnerable to perennial floods due to its low-lying topography, heavy rainfall, and geographical location (Thecla, 2014).

Figure 1. Port Harcourt - the Study Area

The climatic conditions of Port Harcourt are characterized by a tropical climate. Precipitation of considerable magnitude occurs during the majority of months throughout the year. The brief period characterized by aridity does not exert a noteworthy influence on the general climatic conditions. The mean annual rainfall for the study environment is above 2300mm. The data retrieved from close meteorological station presents the mean monthly rainfall distribution for 30 years (1985-2015) in the study area. It showed that average highest rainfall peaks were attained in September (370mm), July (364mm) and August (325mm). Lowest rainfall values were attained in January (15.3mm) and December (19.2mm).

Analysis from the macro data shows that the months of July-September recorded lower temperatures (28-29 o C) due to rainy periods while the months December to March recorded higher temperatures (32 - 34 o C) due to intense solar radiation prevalent in the dry season. Uko and Tamunobereton-Ari, (2013) noted that the average maximum and minimum temperatures during the dry and wet seasons are within 31-33

o C and 21 - 23 o C as well as 25-33 o C and 18 23 o C respectively.

Methodology

This study uses a geographic information system multi-criteria decision analysis (GIS-MCDA) method to identify flood-prone and vulnerable areas in Port Harcourt. The analysis focused on

analysing raster data of elevation, aspect, flow accumulation, flow direction, slope, rainfall, stream distance, soil characteristics, and a binary variable indicating flood occurrence (Training). Table 1 captures the variables and data sources used for the analysis and in developing the flood vulnerability map.

Table 1. Types Variables and Sources of Data Used for the MCDA

SN	Factors	Data Used	Source	Detail	Techniques	Source
1	Elevation	Raster	USGS Earth Explorer	Entity ID: SRTM1N08E 011V3, Date: 2014-09-23, Resolution: 1-ARC		DeWitt, J. D., Warner, T. A., & Conley, J. F. (2015)
2	Slope	Raster	USGS Earth Explorer		Slope Analysis	Pande & Moharir (2017).
3	Aspect	Raster	USGS Earth Explorer		Slope Analysis	Pande & Moharir (2017).
4	Flow Accumulation	Raster	USGS Earth Explorer		Hydrological Analysis	Pande & Moharir (2017).
5	Flow Direction	Raster	USGS Earth Explorer		Hydrological Analysis	Pande & Moharir (2017).
6	Land Surface Temperature	Raster	https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/			Qi, S., Song, B., Liu, C., Gong, P., Luo, J., Zhang, M., & Xiong, T. (2022)
7	Rainfall	Raster	https://www.chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirps			Faisal, M., & Jaelani, L. M. (2023)
8	Land Use	Raster	USGS Earth Explorer		Supervised image classification	Dell et al., (2022)
9	Soil	Polygon Shapefile	Digital Soil of the World			
10	Distance to stream (m)	Polyline	Field Survey (2023)		Euclidian Distance Buffering	Zhou, Zhang & Huang (2021)
11	Flood Locations	Point Shape file	Field Survey (2023)		Digitization process	Ali et al., (2020)

Geospatial data was obtained by downloading them from their respective sources using an internet enabled computer with active data from an internet service provider.

Data Collection and Preparation for Flood Prediction Model

General Settings

- The project's general settings involve creating specific folders for the working directory and personal library.

- The working directory was set to store the processed data and results.
- Necessary packages such as raster, car, rgeos, rgdal, and maptools are installed and loaded.

Loading Raster Data

- Raster data for elevation, aspect, flow accumulation, flow direction, slope, rainfall,

stream distance, soil, and the binary flood occurrence variable were loaded into R objects.

- Resampling was performed to ensure all rasters had the same extent.

Data Preparation

- The slope raster was reclassified to create a categorical map.
- Rasters were resampled to ensure consistency in spatial characteristics.

The raster data was converted to a list, and the values along with coordinates were extracted. The data frames were merged, and NAs are removed to create a clean dataset for analysis.

Results and Discussion

The Flood model consists of vulnerability maps of spatial multi-criteria components referred to as variables here they include: Elevation, Flow Accumulation, Rainfall, Slope, Soil, Distance from Streams and waterbody with Land use. Different maps were produced for the various variables and an eventual overlay of all the maps was used to generate an overall vulnerability map. figure 2. captures the Elevation, Flow Accumulation, Rainfall, and Slope Maps, while figure 3. captures Soil, Distance from Streams and waterbody and Land use maps.

(a) Elevation

(b) Flow Accumulation

(c) Rainfall

(d) Slope

Figure 2. (a)Elevation map; (b)Flow Accumulation map; (c)Rainfall map and (d)Slope map

(a) Soil

(b) Distance from Streams and waterbody

(c) Landuse

Figure 3. (a) Soil map; (b) Distance from stream, water body map and (c) Land use map

Figure 4. Flood Vulnerability Map

Table 2. Flood Vulnerability Profile for the Flood Vulnerability Map

Vulnerability Level	Colour code	Vulnerability Value	Area (Hectare)	Area (SqKM)	Percentage %
Very High Vulnerability	Red	5	2.18	0.0218	0.02
High Vulnerability	Orange	4	5380.29	53.8029	49.87
Moderate Vulnerability	Yellow	3	4372.95	43.7295	40.53
Low Vulnerability	Light green	2	1014.93	10.1493	9.41
Very Low Vulnerability	Green	1	18.11	0.1811	0.17

Table 2. captures information on the vulnerability profile of the study location for figure 4. which is the vulnerability map, the map visualizes vulnerability with colour codes indicating level of vulnerability captured, area covered in Square Kilometres and hectares on table 2. The vulnerability profile from the table is as follows; Very High Vulnerability with Red colour covering 0.0218 Sq. Km making only 0.02 %, High Vulnerability with Orange colour covers 53.8029 Sq. Km making 49.87% of the total area, Moderate Vulnerability with Yellow colour on the map covers 43.7295 Sq. Km making 40.53 %, Low Vulnerability with Light green covers 10.1493 Sq. Km making 9.41%, and Very Low Vulnerability with Green colour covering 0.1811 Sq. km making only 0.17 %.

Logistic Regression ANOVA Result for Flood Model

The result of the ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) presented in table 3. for the statistical analysis of logistic regression model for the flood vulnerability model, ANOVA was used to assess the significance of the different variables used in the flood model in explaining variability in the flood model.

Df (Degrees of Freedom): degrees of freedom associated with each factor or predictor. Deviance represents the reduction in deviance (a measure of how well the flood model fits the data) when each variable is added to the model. It measures how much each variable contributes to explaining the variation in the dependent variable (Flood vulnerability).

Resid. Df (Residual Degrees of Freedom): This indicates the degrees of freedom for the residual deviance, which represents the remaining unexplained variation in the model.

Resid. Dev (Residual Deviance): The residual deviance is a measure of how much unexplained variation is left in the model after accounting for the variables used.

Pr(>Chi) (p-value): The p-value associated with each variable's addition to the model is an indicator of its significance in explaining the variation in the dependent variable. Smaller p-values suggest greater significance.

NULL: This represents the null model, which has no predictor variables. The residual deviance for the null model is 111.888 with 98 degrees of freedom.

Aspect_re: The addition of the "Aspect_re" variable to the model results in a significant reduction in deviance (from 111.888 to 105.000) with 1 degree of freedom. The p-value (0.0086774) is less than 0.05, indicating that "Aspect_re" is statistically significant in explaining the variation in the dependent variable.

Elevation: The addition of the "Elevation" variable leads to a substantial reduction in deviance (from 105.000 to 62.599) with 1 degree of freedom. The p-value (7.434e-11) is highly significant, suggesting that "Elevation" is a significant predictor.

Flow accumulation, Flow direction and Soil: These variables do not contribute significantly to reducing deviance as their p-values are much greater than 0.05. They are not considered statistically significant predictors in this model.

Rainfall, Slope, Distance from Streams and waterbody all contribute significantly to reducing deviance, as indicated by their small p-values. They are considered statistically significant predictors in explaining the variation in the dependent variable (Flood Vulnerability).

Table 3. Logistic Regression ANOVA Result for Flood Model

Df Deviance	Resid.	Df	Resid.	Dev	Pr(>Chi)
NULL			98		111.888
Aspect_re	1	6.888	97	105.000	0.0086774 **
Elevation	1	42.401	96	62.599	7.434e-11 ***
Flow_acc_re	1	0.044	95	62.555	0.8332463
Flow_dir_re	1	2.190	94	60.364	0.1388702
Rainfall_re	1	18.475	93	41.889	1.721e-05 ***
Slope_re	1	13.916	92	27.973	0.0001912 ***
Soil_re	1	0.322	91	27.651	0.5705531
Stream_dis_re	1	19.696	90	7.956	9.081e-06 ***

Note: level of significance: " ($p < 0.001$), indicates a highly significant result " ($p < 0.01$) indicates significant, and " ($p < 0.05$) indicates marginally significant.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the area coverage, the most predominant vulnerability level was High Vulnerability, which accounted for 49.87% of the total area. This was followed by Moderate Vulnerability at 40.53%, Low Vulnerability at 9.41%, Very Low Vulnerability at 0.17%, and Very High Vulnerability at 0.02%. In this context of vulnerability, areas within “Very high” and “High” classes were considered as high flood prone zones, and areas within “Very low” and “Low” classes were considered low flood prone zones (Ajur & Mogheir, 2020).

The High Vulnerability level, which was most prevalent, covering 49.87% of the total area with 53.8029 square kilometres. indicated that a significant portion of the study area faces high susceptibility to flooding. Moderate Vulnerability which followed closely behind at 40.53% (43.7295 sq. km), demonstrates an additional substantial area requiring attention. While the Low Vulnerability (9.41%, 10.1493 sq. km) and Very Low Vulnerability (0.17%, 0.1811 sq. km) together represent a minority of the landscape with lower flood risk.

These findings corroborate with the findings of Ugwu et al., (2022) on the spatial distribution of flood vulnerability in Port Harcourt metropolis. where low vulnerability covered 60.78 sq. km (13.22%), moderate vulnerability extended over 259.72 sq. km (56.51%), and high vulnerability encompassed 139.14 sq. km (30.27%) also indicating that a significant portion of the region faces high susceptibility to flooding.

Identifying the specific locations associated with each vulnerability level is crucial for targeted risk management strategies by utilising the vulnerability map (Fig 4.17) which displays the spatial distribution of vulnerability. Understanding the individual contributions of each component variable (elevation, rainfall, etc.) to the overall vulnerability can also be gleaned from analysing the separate maps in figures 2 and 3. these helps to pinpoint the specific factors driving vulnerability in different areas, for the significance of the different variables used in the flood vulnerability mapping in explaining variability in the flood zones; Rainfall, Slope, Distance from Streams and waterbody all contributed significantly to reducing deviance, as indicated by their small p-values, and so they are considered statistically significant predictors in explaining the variation in the dependent variable (Flood Vulnerability). While Flow accumulation, Flow direction and Soil are not considered to be statistically significant due to their P-values greater than 0.05.

The vulnerability map output provides valuable information for flood mitigation and preparedness efforts. Areas with high and moderate vulnerability call for prioritizing measures like infrastructure improvements, early warning systems, and community awareness campaigns. Additionally, understanding the factors contributing to vulnerability in each area (through analysing individual component maps) will help to better tailor mitigation strategies more effectively.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Geospatial maps have proven to be very ideal and useful when identifying areas that are most vulnerable to flooding. This information can be used to help communities prepare for and mitigate flood risk. Comparing the different vulnerability levels provides information that can be used to help decision-makers allocate resources to areas that are most in need and vulnerable to the impact of flooding, overlaying the map with other data, such as population density or infrastructure, to identify areas that are most at risk of flooding.

Close monitoring and evaluation should be carried out with rapt attention to even the minimal changes in climatic factors as this will help to better anticipate and put in place mitigation plans, which could commence with harmonising existing data on various vulnerability factors and environmental stressors.

Besides, by combining the vulnerability maps with information on population density, infrastructure, and land use, mitigation strategies could be better tailored to specific contexts. This might involve prioritizing early warning systems in densely populated areas or flood-prone locations with critical infrastructure.

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